

POST OCCUPANCY EVALUATION OF BUILDING WAYFINDINGS AND COMFORT IN PUBLIC COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN NORTH-CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study was on post-occupancy evaluation of building wayfindings and comfort in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria (PCENCN). The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study was 933 drawn from the 13 PCENCN. The sample size of the study was 420 respondents, 3 states, and 6 colleges of education being 45% respectively. Two research questions and null hypotheses guided the study respectively. The instrument for data collection was a 15 items structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistical mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while ANOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The findings of the study among others revealed that, there was highly need of building improvement in PCENCN. The finding also revealed that, there were clarities of wayfinding within and around the building complex. However, not all the circulation routes were well understood and convenient to visitors and new students. It was also found that, indoor air quality, quality of building support services and ergonomics of educational facilities did not meet their purposes in PCENCN. It was recommended that, college managements should improve on the wayfinding through modernization to ensure all the circulation routes are well understood and convenient to visitor and future new students. It was also suggested that the college managements should find ways of installing quality central air-conditioning system and the reposition of windows in all the old lecture buildings to eliminate various indoor air quality problems.

Keywords: Post Occupancy Evaluation, Context and Wayfinding.

Introduction

Post occupancy evaluation (POE) is the process of evaluating building in use systematically and comprehensively to identify the major areas of success and failures with view to provide feedback for improvement. In other words, post-occupancy evaluation is assessment toolkit designed to address problems in building design and construction, through comprehensive studies of buildings after they have been built and occupied (Zagreus, 2014). What makes POE process differs significantly from other conventional surveys is that it uses direct unmediated experiences of building users as the basis for evaluating how a building performance meets its intended use. Therefore, the usually targeted groups of POE during data collection are the users and occasionally the professionals (architects, builders and others).

POE gives opportunity to building user to participate in the building evaluation process, and this makes them to take more ownership of the building. This study investigated wayfindings and users' comforts in post

occupancy lecture hall buildings and built environments of 60s–80s in public colleges of education in North Central, Nigeria.

Wayfinding is the accessibility of building users to reach and get out of a building effortlessly when finding their routes to their destinations within and around building complex. Wayfinding is the process of finding your ways or routes to a destination in a familiar or unfamiliar setting using any cues given by the environment (Anna, 2012). In this regards, Callum (2020) stated that building users should not be confused, frustrated, or stressed in finding their routes/ways within and around school building complex. Most a time signage, permanent landmarks and neighbourhood interaction are used as cues to locate a destination.

Comfort is inherently linked to human pleasant and favourable working environment that allows individual to perform their work optimally under comfortable condition and promotes users' wellbeing. Building Comfort is therefore an appealing, pleasant and favourable condition that the users derive while in a building (Paul, 2015).

Building facilities users should feel generally comfortable in all building facility indices. That demands that building indoor environment must not be too hot or too cool with reference to thermal and temperature conditions. It must not be dirty, dark, too glare and noisy as these may cause physical and psychological ill feelings (horror). Comfort in building is achieved through the performances of cluster of indoor and outdoor environmental factors, which depends largely on design quality and continuous improvement (Zhiben, Yuxin, and Liang, 2022). Some building factors that influence users comfort include; workspace, temperature, indoor air quality, lighting, sound/noise level, thermal, sun glare, cleanliness, dirt, furnishings and arrangement. Building and its environmental qualities are therefore core indispensable determinant factors of users' comfort and educational program achievement (Uche and Okata, 2015).

The study evaluated building wayfinding and users' comforts, and provided feedback and recommendations. It is hoped that the findings of the study would serve as the beginning of stakeholders' awareness in other to make necessary improvement needs on old lecture buildings in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

There has been general outcry by members of public, and evidently supported by several national dailies and research reports that, most building elements and other built environments developed across the nation in the 60s - 80s in public tertiary institutions were poorly designed, constructed and ageing, and are presently in deplorable condition. It is also speculated that, since their occupancy, no appropriate building assessments have been carried out on them for possible improvement, to actually meet this modern age educational needs and aspiration. Consequently, it is attested that most of these buildings for one reason or the other no longer support, but frustrate educational programs of this age (Ayuba, 2015; Marwa, Mohammed, Ibrahim & Tarak, 2018; & Izran, 2020).

Evidently to the above assertions, the researcher having visited few Public Colleges of Education in Benue and Plateau States in North Central, Nigeria, observed that, some lecturers and students' complained of improvement needs of lecture hall buildings and built environments in the 60s - 80s, because of ageing and out of date design, non - availability/poor building performance indicators (building layout, design quality, building appearance and accessibility), and environmental unfriendliness (discomfort).

In a similar development, some groups of new students particularly complained of poorly designed, inadequate and non-availability of wayfinding cues, thus, making findings of routes to some offices, departments and other areas of students' interest within the campus difficult. They specifically, lamented that, often they missed or arrived late to tests, examinations and appointments due to difficulties in finding specified activities locations. They equally complained that visitors and new students often found it difficult to locate places and their wards during visiting days or school events because of poor and non-availability of wayfinding cues where necessary.

The most unfortunate complaint arose from few lecturers and students who generally complained of indoor environmental quality unfriendliness while in lecture halls. They specifically pointed out some key areas of building discomfort to include poorly designed indoor environmental quality comfort indices (indoor air quality, quality of lighting, workspace, acoustic, visual, thermal, accessibility, sun glare, furnishings and arrangement, serviceability and building appearance).

This development is worrisome, and is the motivation behind this study. In the course of literature reviews, the researcher discovered that there existed dearth of local literatures on wayfinding, except few on comfort, especially concerning Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. Is an indication that, perhaps the researchers have not seen the need of researching in to these sensitive areas of building, hence, there are existing gaps to fill in terms of local literatures, and the creating of awareness especially, to the college managements, Federal and State Governments who are the owners of these colleges under this study. The researcher equally wants to bring to the knowledge of potential researchers to see these as virgin areas of research. Thus, this study evaluated building wayfinding with feedback for possible improvements.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is post-occupancy evaluation of building wayfinding and users' comfort in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine;

- 1 The extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around building complex
- 2 The extent to which the buildings have affected lecturers and students' comfort

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent is the clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex?
2. To what extent have the buildings affected lecturers and students' comfort?

Hypotheses

The following two hypotheses guided the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of architects, lecturers, and students on the extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex.
2. There is no significance difference in the mean responses of architects, lecturers, and students on the extent to which the buildings have affected lecturers and students' comfort.

Research Methodology

The study adopted survey research design. The area of the study was North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The population of the study was 933 drawn from the 13 public colleges of education in North Central, Nigeria. The composition of the population included 13 architects, 300 lecturers and 620 students. The sample of the study was 420 respondents, 6 colleges of education and 3 states being 45% respectively was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a 15 items structured questionnaire titled “Post Occupancy Evaluation of Building wayfinding and users’ comfort Questionnaire (POEBWCQ)”.

Four hundred and twenty (420) questionnaires were administered with the help of 6 trained research assistants. The questionnaires were all returned which represented 100% return. The questionnaire was divided into three sections (Section A-C). Section “A” was on respondents’ personal data, section “B” consisted of questions on building wayfinding, while section “C” contained questions on building comfort. Meanwhile, the numerical rating values of questionnaire on section “B” was based on a seven point rating scale ranging from; Very Unsatisfactory (VU=1); Unsatisfactory (U=2); Somewhat Unsatisfactory (SU=3); Somewhat satisfactory (SS=4); Satisfactory (S=5); Neither (N=6); and Very Satisfactory (VS=7); While that of questionnaire on section C was based on a seven point rating scale ranging from; Very highly unmet (VHUM=1); Highly unmet (HUM=2); Somewhat met (SM=3); Neither Met (NM=4); Somewhat unmet (SUM=5); Highly met (HM=6); and Very Highly Met (VHM=7).

The instrument was content and face validated by three experts from the Department of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria, Department of Vocational Teachers’ Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, and Department of Architectural Design, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue State respectively. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Descriptive statistical mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. The choice of ANOVA was because the study was design to examine the potential differences among the three categories of respondents (Lecturer, architects and students).

Results

Research Question One

To what extent is the clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Response on the Clarity of Wayfinding Within and Around the Building Complex

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
1.	There are sufficient easy routes, pathways, streets and passageways provided to and within the college building complex.	420	6.53	1.87	Very satisfactory
2.	There are routes that link the building to the surrounding structures within the campus.	420	5.29	1.69	Satisfactory
3.	The routes are arranged well, considering the busy periods, quiet periods, one - way traffic, regular movement patters and traffic jams.	420	5.54	1.16	Satisfactory
4.	There are meeting points for traffic around the building.	420	6.28	1.28	Very Satisfactory
5.	All the circulation routes are well understandable and convenient to all.	420	3.17	0.77	Somewhat Unsatisfactory
6.	All the circulation routes within the building are easily understand by new students and visitors.	420	3.28	0.89	Somewhat Unsatisfactory
7.	All the interior circulation routes are clearly marked and easy to understand.	420	5.43	1.01	Satisfactory
8.	The locations of lecturers' offices are easily accessible.	420	4.76	1.18	Somewhat satisfactory

Table 1 revealed the mean and standard deviation scores of clarities of wayfinding within and around the building complex in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. The data in table 1 showed that, the mean scores responses of respondents on items 1 and 4 with standard deviation of 1.87 and 1.28 are considered very satisfactory; items 2, 3, 7 and 8 are with mean scores of 5.29, 5.54, 5.43 and 4. 76 with standard deviation of 1.69, 1.16, 1.01 and 1.01, are considered satisfactory, while items 5 and 6 are with mean scores of 3.17 and 3.28 with standard deviation of 0.77 and 0.89, are considered somewhat satisfactory. This implies that, there are clarities of wayfinding within and around the building complex in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria, however, not all the circulation routes were well understood and convenient to visitors and the new students.

Research Question Two

To what extent have the building affected lecturers and students' comfort?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Response on the Building Affected Lecturers and Students' Comfort

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
1.	The learning spaces in the lecture rooms suit individual thermal comfort.	420	1.46	0.37	Very unsatisfactory
2.	Device to adjust thermal comfort is suitable for individual in the lecture room and other areas of student meetings.	420	1.89	0.58	Unsatisfactory
3.	The lighting level in the lecture hall support learning spaces.	420	1.68	0.51	Unsatisfactory
4.	The noise level in the typical learning space is very not distracting and irritating.	420	1.86	0.57	Unsatisfactory
5.	The chair and the table in the lecture rooms are very comfortable and easily moveable without damaging the floor.	420	1.49	0.67	Very Unsatisfactory
6.	The lecture room temperature provides weather condition that is not too cold and not too hot in all round the year.	420	2.77	1.09	Somewhat Unsatisfactory
7.	The lecture rooms have effective operative windows that control weather conditions such as indoor air quality, dust, incoming wind and glare.	420	2.35	1.01	Unsatisfactory

Table 2 reveals the mean and standard deviation scores of building affected lecturers and students' comfort in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. The data in table 2 showed that, the mean scores for the responses of respondents on items 1, 2, 3 4, 5, 6 and 7 were 1.46, 1.89, 1.68, 1.86, 1.49, 2.77 and 2.35 with standard deviation scores of 0.37, 0.58, 0.51, 0.57, 0.67, 1.09 and 1.01 respectively, which are considered very unsatisfactory. This implies that, building affected lecturers and students' comfort in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. By implication, the workspaces in the lecture rooms did not suit individual thermal comfort. The devices to adjust thermal comfort are not readily available, and the noise level in the typical learning spaces is very distracting and irritating.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of architects, lecturers, and students on the extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex.

Table 3: Result for ANOVA Analysis of Variance on Extent of Clarity of Wayfinding within and Around the Building Complex

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4.572	2	2.286	5.635	.004
Within Groups	169.193	417	.406		
Total	173.765	419			

Table 4: Tukey HSD Post Hoc Comparison on Extent of Clarity of Wayfinding Within and Around the Building Complex

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign.
Students	Architects	-.83533*	.263	.001
Lecturers	Architects	-.74582*	.266	.014
Lecturers	Students	.08951	.067	.374

ANOVA analysis result in Table 3 revealed that, there is a significant variation among the mean responses of lecturers, students and architects on the extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex [F_{2, 419} = 5.635, P < 0.05]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that, there is a significant variation in the mean responses of lecturers, students and architects on the extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex in public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Table 4 shows Tukey HSD post-hoc comparison on extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex. The results revealed that the mean difference (I-J) between students and architects is -.83533* and this is significant at p < 0.05. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean responses rating between the students and architects on the extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex. The results also revealed that the mean difference (I-J) between lecturers and architects is -.74582* and this is significant at p < 0.05. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean responses rating between the lecturer and architects on the extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex. Likewise, the paired comparison of lecturers and students showed a mean difference of .08951 and this is not significant at p > 0.05. This indicates no significant difference in the mean responses rating between lecturers and students on the extent of clarity of wayfinding within and around the building complex in public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significance difference in the mean responses of architects, lecturers and students on the extent to which the building have affected lecturers and students’ comfort.

Table 5: Result for Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Extent to Which the Building Have Affected Lecturers and Students' Comfort

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.286	2	1.143	9.620	.000
Within Groups	49.534	417	.119		
Total	51.820	419			

Table 6: Tukey HSD Post Hoc Comparison on Extent to Which the Building Have Affected Lecturers and Students' Comfort

(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sign.
Students	Architects	-.60276*	.142	.000
Lecturers	Architects	-.63074*	.144	.000
Lecturers	Students	.02798	.036	.719

ANOVA analysis result in Table 5 revealed that, there is a significant variation among the mean responses of lecturers, students and architects on the extent to which the building have affected lecturers and students' comfort [F_{2, 419} = 9.620, P < 0.05]. The null hypothesis is therefore, rejected. This implies that, there is a significant variation in the mean responses of lecturers, students and architects on the extent to which the building have affected lecturers and students' comfort in public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Table 6 shows Tukey HSD post-hoc comparison on the extent to which the buildings have affected lecturers and students' comfort. The results revealed that the mean difference (I-J) between students and architects is -.60276* and this is significant at p < 0.05. This implies that there is a significant variation in the mean responses rating between the students and architects on the extent to which the buildings have affected lecturers and students' comfort. The results also revealed that the mean difference (I-J) between lecturers and architects is -.63074* and this is significant at p < 0.05. This implies that there is significant variation in the mean responses rating between the lecturer and architects on the extent to which the building has affected lecturers and students' comfort. Likewise, the paired comparison of lecturers and students showed a mean difference of .02798 and this is not significant at p > 0.05. This indicated no significant variations in the mean responses rating between lecturers and students on the extent to which the building has affected lecturers and students' comfort in public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study focused on post occupancy evaluation of building wayfinding and users building comfort in public colleges of education in North-Central, Nigeria. It found that, there are sufficient easy routes, pathways,

streets and passageways provided to and within the college building complex. There are routes that link the building to the surrounding structures within the campus. The routes are well arranged, considering the busy periods, quiet periods, one-way traffic, regular movement patterns and traffic jams. It was also revealed that, there are meeting points for traffic around the building. All the interior circulation routes are clearly marked and easy to understand and the locations of lecturers' offices are easily accessible in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. The result of this finding is in agreement with the finding of Adebayo, Ayuba, Olagunju, Adamu and Audu (2013) who revealed that users wayfinding of location of facilities in Public Building Design in Selected Cities in Nigeria is a major problem.

It was also revealed that, the learning spaces in the lecture rooms did not suit individual thermal comfort and devices to adjust thermal comfort are not suitable for individual in the lecture room and other areas of student meetings. The lighting level in the lecture hall did not support learning spaces and the noise level in the typical learning space is very distracting and irritating in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. In the same vein, it was revealed that, the chair and the table in the lecture rooms are not very comfortable and the lecture rooms in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria did not have effective operative windows that can control weather conditions such as indoor air quality, cold or hot, dust, incoming wind and glare. This finding is in line with Saleem, Shah and Ihsan (2016) findings that interior physical environment of Pakistan higher education institutions is not conducive for academicians' productivity.

Conclusion

It is evident from the findings of this study that, there are clarities of wayfinding within and around the building complex. However, not all the circulation routes are well understandable and convenient to visitors. It was also concluded that, indoor air quality (temperature, ventilation/thermal comfort), acoustic comfort (noise level), visual comfort (quality of day or electricity lighting), quality of building supply and services (water supply and water closet) and ergonomics of educational facilities did not meet their purposes in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations made are:

1. College managements should improvise means or patterns to ensure all the circulation routes are well understandable and convenient to visitors.
2. College managements and relevant agencies should install good central air-conditioning system to building in Public College of Education in North Central to eliminate indoor air quality problems.
3. Quality water supply and water closet within and outside building should be in Public College of Education in North Central to eliminate water supply problems.

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